

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: Mishra****FIRST NAME: Arushi****PROGRAM CODE:DIPH****COURSE CODE : ACA 401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 01****INSTRUCTOR: Pr. Laurent Cleenewerck****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did not use Zotero to insert referencesThe author did not use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

JOURNEY OF ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

Academic writing is one of the vital components of a student's journey. Though looks simple but it involves varied intricacies that a student should keep in mind while writing a paper. This paper discusses the importance of language selection, steps in writing a paper, rules of thumb and style guide selection for paper writing.

2) STEPS TO AN IDEAL PAPER

A good essay should be planned and methodical. The steps to it should include starting with defining the topic for the paper. It is to be followed by researching over the topic (ACA-401D Course Pack: Period 1 2015, 3). This would help get a perspective of other authors and researchers. Organizing the ideas and finally penning them down in the form of an essay would follow it. The final steps in the paper writing should be referencing for giving the due credits to the authors and proof reading for any mistakes.

To know key facts about plagiarism and citations are essential if you do not want your paper to be rejected. Plagiarism is including a piece of information in the paper without giving credit to the author of that source. Citation on the other hand defines the source of information (ACA-401D Course Pack: Period 1 2015, 14).

Paraphrasing too is a plus in the paper when there are too many quotes to be included. Though it should be done with caution so that it is not just re-phrasing the words or else it will be caught in plagiarism again.

a) Thumb Rules

Thumb rules are a go to points for paper writing. To begin with, the main hypothesis should be introduced in the opening paragraph. Throughout the paper, the author needs stay pivoted on the subject and not get carried away with the overview of the subject matter. Generalized statements should be avoided as it gives an idea of beating around the bush. The sentences should be crisp and clear (ACA-401D Course Pack: Period 1 2015, 43).The writing should be innovative and not lousy so that the readers are engaged till the end. Evidence throughout the paper are always helpful and gives credibility to the author. Read you paper aloud before submission to discover minor errors that may have been overlooked.

b) American Vs. British English

Post the World War II; American English has increased its momentum of popularity. It is mainly because of the higher population of US compared to UK, the economic increase in the US, the magnanimous publication and education hub and political position the US holds.

There are many differences, one of them being that a few words that are spelled the same but pronounced differently. For example words like advertisement, oregano, harass. There are a few words on the contrary that are pronounced the same but spelled differently. For example colour – color, alright – all right. The punctuation marks too differ in both languages in date writing, business letter salutations and honorifics.

There are different terms of expression for conceptually the same thing. For example two weeks may also be referred to as a fortnight and a bank holiday may also be referred to as a public holiday.

i) *Chicago Style and Usage*

It is the style of formatting books and academic papers as per the Chicago Manual of Style (CMS). Spell check from Webster's Third New International dictionary is recommended (EUCLID 2015, 66).Abbreviations should not be constant practice while writing a paper. It should be used keeping in view that the reader easily comprehends it. It also emphasizes on capitalization depending of the heading where full caps will be used and sentences where initial first letter will be in caps. Subsequently,the understanding of compound words is essential if they are being included in the paper. Adjectival compound words such as 'role-playing'; made up compounds for example, up-to-date (EUCLID 2015, 68).Additionally,use of hyphens becomes crucial while using compound words. These sentences in papers could use words in italic more for highlighting and getting the attention of the reader.

ii) *Page Formats*

Margins, fonts and indents form the pillars of formatting a paper. The usual dimensions being, 8.5 by 12 inches. A margin of 1 inch is to left from all the four sides. 12-point typeface of Times New Roman is the best choice and a standard indent of one-half inch (EUCLID 2015, 72).

Headings are to be divided into three levels with the main heading being in full caps and one inch from the margin of the paper. It is followed by a first level heading in heading caps, the second level heading in italics and heading caps which is eventually followed by a third level heading which is run in paragraph heading.

Tables if any should be included towards the end of a paragraph with an evident heading for each row and column (EUCLID 2015, 74). Finally, endnotes and footnotes to be included in a specific format considering the number of authors, in which case the first three names followed by et al. should be written. For reports and papers, the name of the author followed by the name of the paper in quotes and in brackets the journal or the conference where it was presented with specific month and year.

3) **CONCLUSION**

In this paper, we have explored the journey for writing an ideal academic paper. Key steps should be instilled in mind for effective paper writing. A thorough research on the topic is the basic need for any paper. It should be then followed by cautiously selecting the language and style that we want to follow in the paper. Give due credits to avoid plagiarism and follow the style rules throughout the paper. Finally format the paper and proof read the same before submission to avoid errors and rejection.

REFERENCES

Euclid University. (n.d.). ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 1. Retrieved from:
<http://www.eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-1/>(accessed 25-04- 2019).

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.